

D6.2 / Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CI/CD	Continuous integration, continuous delivery, and continuous deployment
dBm	Digital biomarker
DMP	Data management plan
DMT	Data management team
EC	European Commission
EPO	European Patent Office
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
HCPs	Healthcare Professionals
HW	Hardware
ICT	Information and communication technologies
IP	Intellectual property
IPR	Intellectual property rights
ISRCTN	International Traditional Medicine Clinical Trial Registry
KER	Key exploitable results
KPI	Key performance indicator
MAFEIP	Monitoring and Assessment Framework for the European Innovation Partnership
ML	Machine learning
MVP	Minimum viable product
OS	Open science
PsA	Psoriatic Arthritis
PsO	Psoriasis
R&I	Research and Innovation
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises

SW	Software
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work package
WWW	World Wide Web
xAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Executive summary

This document is the deliverable D6.2 “Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan” which identifies in detail dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy (including stakeholders’ analysis), plan, language and impact evaluation.

The objective of the current document is to provide guidelines on the different dissemination and communication activities that are planned and designed to reach a broad range of stakeholders, what tools and channels are available for dissemination and what are the actions planned to achieve the exploitation of the results and impact of the project.

The deliverable moreover explains how activities will be performed and their impact monitored.

This is alive document and will be modified according to the project needs. An updated version of the project’s dissemination, exploitation and communication plan will be submitted in M27 through the deliverable D6.8 “Update on the Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan”.

Reports, focusing on results and activities implemented will be provided through the whole project’s implementation period as deliverables D6.3 “First report on project visibility and educational material” (M18), D6.5 “Midterm report on project visibility and education material” (M32) and D6.6 “Final report on project visibility and education material” at the end of the project (M48), D6.4 “Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (initial version)” (M27), and D6.7 “Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (final version)” (M48).

1 Introduction and scope

1.1 Introduction

This document is the second deliverable of the WP6 “Dissemination, communication and exploitation” and is part of the Task 6.1 “Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring” and Task 6.2 “Clustering and networking activities”, the main aims of which are planning, conducting, and monitoring all the dissemination, communication and networking activities of the project.

1.2 Document scope

The purpose of this deliverable is to set the strategic framework and identify in detail dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy (including stakeholders’ analysis), plan, language and impact evaluation.

The Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan defines the goals, the overall strategy and the needed activities in order to:

- Inform about and promote the project and its results;
- Describe and ensure results available for others to use;
- Make concrete use of the project’s results.

The current document provides guidelines on the different dissemination and communication activities that are planned to reach a broad range of stakeholders, what tools and channels are available for dissemination and what are the actions planned to achieve the exploitation of the results and impact of the project.

This deliverable is alive and will be modified according to the project needs.

SMARTSOL SIA leads this task and is responsible for planning, implementation, monitoring, and coordination of activities, DBC leads exploitation planning activities, while the rest of the partners contribute to the plan, communication/dissemination, exploitation activities and reporting.

1.3 Document structure

This document establishes the basis for the development of a common dissemination, exploitation and communication plan in the iPROLEPSIS project. It is intended to give an overview of the types of dissemination, exploitation and communication activities planned during the project, valorise the results of the project, and bring it to the public and to the market.

The present report is organized as follows:

- Executive summary provides summary of the whole document.
- Section 1 introduces the main vision and scope of iPROLEPSIS dissemination, exploitation and communication plan.
- Section 2 introduces definitions and terminology; specific dissemination and communication rules; sets out the core priorities and objectives of the document in detail; defines dissemination and communication approach, actions and activities; identifies in detail stakeholders; introduces the evaluation and monitoring of KPIs; and defines exploitation strategy.
- Finally, Section 3 concludes the document with relevant conclusions.

2 Dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy

2.1 Definitions and terminology

Dissemination, exploitation and communication is an important part of the Horizon Europe (HORIZON) projects, and all consortium partners have to contribute to it.

iPROLEPSIS distinguishes between communication, dissemination, and exploitation (knowledge transfer), in line with the EC¹ definitions below:

Dissemination is the public disclosure of the project results by any appropriate, including scientific publication in any medium. It is the process of promotion and awareness-raising right from the beginning of a project. It makes research results known to various stakeholder groups (e.g., research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers) in a targeted way, enabling them to use the results in their own work. This process must be planned and organised at the beginning of each project. Activities used for dissemination purposes are for example a public website, press releases, publications, and attendance at events.

Communication is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the project and continues throughout its entire lifetime. It is aimed at promoting iPROLEPSIS results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) iPROLEPSIS and (ii) results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. Activities used for communication purposes are for example a public website, social media, or a newsletter.

Exploitation of results requires several steps including identifying exploitation mechanisms and activities. It focuses on identified end-users to ensure impact and uptake of the results. Exploitation can only start once the research results are available. It focuses on making concrete use of research results for commercial, societal, and political purposes. Depending on the nature and scope of the project, there is a wide spectrum of results that may be recognised as exploitable, including policy recommendations or standardisation activities.

2.2 Objectives and links with other project activities

To ensure the successful implementation of the pathways towards impact in long-term, the project consortium aims at making iPROLEPSIS a reference for the fight against PsA. This goal requires dedication from all partners and effective management from the coordination team in order to reach and engage a wide range of different actors.

The core priorities in the iPROLEPSIS Dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy are organized around three complimentary actions as follows:

- Dissemination actions;
- Exploitation actions;
- Communication activities.

¹https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

In this manner, the aim of the iPROLEPSIS Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan is to promulgate findings and outputs of the project to key stakeholders to create value within the target communities and initiatives in the EU.

This deliverable is part of the Work Package 6 on dissemination, exploitation and communication, which objectives are to:

- Maximise visibility of the project (outcomes) and facilitate knowledge exchange, through careful planning, implementation and monitoring of dissemination, communication and networking activities;
- Develop PsA-related educational content;
- Set out a roadmap for regulatory approval of the iPROLEPSIS digital tools;
- Perform a thorough socio-economic/market analysis and develop concrete joint/individual exploitation plans.

WP6 is a transversal work package integrating the results of all the WPs for the dissemination, communication and exploitation process: it will ensure that the outputs and learnings arising from all the activities of the project are visible to the wider audience, can be learned from and implemented on a European scale.

Figure 1 Interrelation of WP6 with other WPs

WP6 activities are anchored in four central tasks:

- Task 6.1 Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring;
- Task 6.2 Clustering and networking activities;
- Task 6.3 PsA educational content development;
- Task 6.4 Regulatory approval and exploitation strategy.

The activities of these tasks will ensure openness, visibility and reuse of iPROLEPSIS outcomes through open science, effective dissemination/communication and strategic networking/joint activities.

T6.1 focuses on planning, conducting and monitoring all the dissemination and communication activities of the project. Besides, the task will highlight on creating an active iPROLEPSIS community of stakeholders, increasing the awareness and visibility of the project results.

T6.1 is closely related to T6.2 where clustering and networking activities to raise awareness, exchange knowledge and communicate the project vision and outcomes to key stakeholder groups are foreseen.

T6.3 focuses on the development of educational content about PsA. To create the material, the task will work in close collaboration with the project's clinical partners (WP5).

Reports, focusing on T6.1, T6.2 and T6.3 results and activities implemented will be provided through the whole project's period as deliverables D6.3 "First report on project visibility and educational material" (month 18), D6.5 "Midterm report on project visibility and education material" (month 32) and D6.6 "Final report on project visibility and education material" at the end of the project (month 48).

In collaboration with Task 1.5 "Innovation and intellectual property management" from WP1, regulatory approval and exploitation strategy will be prepared and exploitable outcomes of the project identified (T6.4). This will contribute to the deliverables D6.4 "Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (initial version)" (month 27), and D6.7 "Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (final version)" (month 48).

On higher scale, the dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy is dependent on all WPs in disseminating results and outputs to specific stakeholders, defining exploitable outputs, thus active input from content related WP partners is expected, not only through their results and deliverables, but also by identifying key audience of their results.

The current document is considered as a 'living document', i.e., and therefore it will be enhanced and adapted during the project as required. Report as a deliverable D6.8. "Update on the Dissemination and Communication plan" will be submitted at the project's month 27.

2.3 Dissemination and communication approach

The dissemination strategy of iPROLEPSIS outputs aims at:

- **informing key stakeholders** about results and their clinical innovation potential;
- **making the outputs widely available** for research and business purposes in the long term.

Dissemination efforts will be put in place along with the first scientific results and carried on throughout the whole project duration.

In doing that, the dissemination will be based on **3 pathways**:

1. **Publications** in peer-reviewed journals and business magazines;
2. **Dissemination events**, such as clinical, research and business conferences, workshops, special sessions, seminars and clinical focus groups with patients;
3. **Media presence**, such as newsletters, website/blog, social media posts or local/national major media (TV and radio) presentation.

Dissemination will largely rely on existing consortium partners' contact research and business networks in the fields of rheumatology, dermatology and general practice, as well as computer science and medical AI, also leveraging their institutional communication channels (e.g., websites, social media, newsletters).

Regarding the scientific publications, the Open Research Europe platform will be used along with prestigious high-impact journals under open access conditions (**Paragraph 2.7.3**).

Table 1 Main elements of the dissemination actions

Dissemination pillar	What	When	Main Target Audience	Purpose
Publications	Peer-reviewed journals	From M18 when solid scientific results will be available	Academia	Communicate scientific findings and take feedback
	Business Magazines		Industry	Inform industries (medical devices, pharma, etc.) about the project's vision
Event participation	Scientific conference presentations/posters	From M12 when initial scientific results will be available	Academia	Communicate scientific findings and take feedback
	Business/Industry events, and EXPOs stands/booths		Industry	Inform industry about the project's vision and exchange ideas
	Workshops/Special sessions/Seminars	From M18 when solid scientific results will be available	Academia, Clinicians	Communicate scientific findings and take feedback
	Clinical focus groups with patients	From M14 when the study applications will be available	Clinician, Patients	Increase engagement of the participants of the studies
Media presence	Newsletters	From M3 every three months	Patients, Authorities, General public	Attract the interest of relevant stakeholders, e.g., patients, hospitals, clinicians, associations, municipalities
	Website/blog posts	From M1		
	Social media posts	From M1		
	Major media (TV/radio) presence	From M36 when tangible results will have produced		

Communication activities will support dissemination and outreach objectives while targeting stakeholders' society at large, including citizens, patients, HCPs, relevant R&I projects and policy makers, at EU and national level. The Communication of iPROLEPSIS is strategically planned and identifies and sets clear communication objectives and uses pertinent messages, right medium and means.

The **main objectives of the communication activities** of the project are:

1. **Increasing people with/at risk of PsA engagement** for addressing their issues and concerns in order to increase their awareness and to build trust into new technology;
2. **Reaching similar/relevant R&I projects** for promoting networking and joint activities;
3. **Establishing a forum/community for HCPs and authorities** to develop new guidelines and standards.

Communication activities will start right after the project inception and will be carried out during its lifecycle, encompassing **the following phases**:

1. **Stakeholder analysis**: based on the identified audiences, the consortium will make a targeted search of institutions, associations, foundations, businesses, professionals to be engaged for communication purposes;
2. **Formulation of diversified messages, languages, and contents** for different target audiences;
3. **Conception and design of a coherent project branding** to achieve an effective visual identity, including logo, infographics, banners for acknowledgments of EU funding, to be included in all materials relevant to communication, dissemination, IPR and on equipment, infrastructure, and major results;
4. **Set up of different communication channels**: website, social networks to be populated with project news and achievements, further contributing to the growth of its communities of interest, and an open access publication archive within the Zenodo OpenAIRE public repository;
5. **Preparation of diversified communication materials**: print-based (brochures, posters); multimedia (photos, teaser videos, interviews, demos), to be spread through website and social media.

Table 2 Communication messages and channels

Objective/ Message to communicate	Communication channel	Level	Main target audience
Project progress	Website; Social media; Newsletters; Major media presence	National, EU, Worldwide	General public
Patient engagement	Clinical focus groups; Newsletters; Social media; Major media presence	National, EU	Patients
Extending network	Conferences; Business events; Workshops; Special sessions; Seminars	EU, Worldwide	Academia, Clinicians, Industry
Building a community/forum	Mailing list; Virtual space/room; Conferences/events	EU, Worldwide	Academia, Clinicians, Industry
Dissemination of scientific results	Publications; Conferences posters/presentations; Workshops; Special sessions	Worldwide	Academia

Timetable for dissemination activities is presented below (**Figure 2**)

The partners' participation in scientific conferences, business and industry events is foreseen from M12, when initial scientific results will be available. From M14, after study applications are developed, workshops, special sessions, seminars and clinical focus groups with patients will be organized. Starting from M18, solid scientific results will be published in peer-reviewed journals, business magazines and presented in workshops, special sessions and seminars.

- **business/industry events** to inform industry about project's findings and exchange ideas;
- **Workshops/seminars/special sessions** to communicate scientific findings and take feedback;
- **Clinical focus groups** to increase engagement of the participants of the studies.

It is expected project partners to participate in at least:

- **20 scientific conferences;**
- **3 business/industry events;**
- **8 workshops/sessions/seminars;**
- **6 patient focus groups.**

The project partners have already identified a list of relevant events and conferences to which participation could be envisaged. This preliminary list, which will be updated throughout the duration of the project, is available below.

Table 3 Preliminary list of events

Planned to attend event / conference	Date of the event	Link
EULAR (European Rheumatology meeting)	June each year	https://congress.eular.org/
ACR (American Rheumatology meeting)	November each year	https://rheumatology.org/annual-meeting
GRAPPA (PsA meeting international)	July each year	https://www.grappanetwork.org/events/2023-annual-meeting-and-trainee-symposium/
EMBC (Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society)	July each year	https://embc.embs.org/
ICASSP (IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing)	Not fixed	https://embc.embs.org/2024/
CVPR workshops (Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition)	June each year	https://cvpr2023.thecvf.com/
HCI (International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction)	July each year	https://2023.hci.international/
CBMS (IEEE International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems)	June-July each year	https://2023.cbms-conference.org/#:~:text=The%2036th%20IEEE%20International%20Symposium,Saturday%2024th%20of%20June%202023.
MEDICA (medical technology trade fair)	November each year	https://www.medicatradefair.com/
Open Living Lab days	September each year	https://openlivinglabdays.com/
IEEE BHI-BSN	Not fixed	https://bhi.embs.org/2023/
Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)	July 2024	https://embc.embs.org/2024/welcome/

SPIE Photonics West	January 2022	https://spie.org/conferences-and-exhibitions/photonics-west
IEEE International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging	May 2024	https://2023.biomedicalimaging.org/en/
ACSM (American College of Sports Medicine)	May each year	https://www.acsm.org/annual-meeting/annual-home
ASBMR (American Society of bone and mineral)	October each year	https://www.asbmr.org/annual-meeting
ICFSR (International Conference on Frailty and Sarcopenia Research)	March 2024	https://frailty-sarcopenia.com/
Events organized by partners	Date of event	Link
Congresso Português de Reumatologia	25-28 October 2023 (annually)	https://spreumatologia.pt/congresso-anual/
AGENT workshop (Multimodal AI signal sensing and AI algorithms in assistive environments for improving quality-of-life) as part of PETRA (Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments Conference)	June each year	http://www.petrae.org/past.html
VITALISE Summer school	June 2023	https://vitalise-project.eu/vitalise-summer-school-2023-on-living-labs/
Society of Applied Neuroscience (SAN) conference	Bi-annually (not fixed)	
Aristotle Medical Forum (AMF)	Annually	
Other relevant events	Date of event	Link
HIMSS (European health conference and exhibition)	June each year	https://www.himss.org/event-himss-europe
European Public health conference	8-11 November 2023	https://ephconference.eu/
European Public health conference	11 - 14 November 2025	https://ephconference.eu/future-conferences-24
World Health Day	April each year	https://www.who.int/campaigns/world-health-day
European Health Forum Gastein	26 - 29 September	https://www.ehfg.org/
Radical Health Festival Helsinki	June 2023	https://radicalhealthfestival.mesukeskus.com/registration/

The participation of partners in events will be made visible through the iPROLEPSIS website and social media channels contributing to increase the community of stakeholders and public interested in the project.

2.4.3 Clustering and networking activities

As part of T6.2, the project partners will undertake clustering and networking activities to raise awareness, exchange knowledge and communicate the project vision and outcomes to key stakeholder groups (e.g., policy formulators, decision makers, healthcare professionals, PsO and PsA organisations, private companies). More specifically, the consortium partners will participate or organise different campaigns, events, joint workshops, etc.

EU projects and initiatives that are considered more relevant for iPROLEPSIS in the field to establish ecosystem of collaboration through which experience, materials and results will be exchanged to stimulate mutual growth have been shortlisted (Table 4) (including the so-called “sister projects“ that have been funded by the European Commission under the same call) and are planned to be reached out in the upcoming months to create synergies and maximize impact. This list will be updated during the whole duration of the project.

Table 4 Preliminary list of R&I projects, initiatives for clustering and networking

Project	Link
AIDA	link
CARE-IN-HEALTH	link
ENDOTARGET	link
GlycanTrigger	link
halt-RONIN	link
IMMEDIATE	link
INITIALISE	link
INTERCEPT-T2D	link
miGut-Health	link
PRAESIIDIUM	link
PREVALUNG EU	link
PROTO	link
VITALISE H2020	link
RAISE HE	link
European Research Area Network on Personalised Medicine (ERAPerMed)	link
International Consortium for Personalised Medicine (ICPerMed)	link
A PeRsOnalised Prevention roadmap for the future HEaLThcare in Europe (PROPHET)	link
WINTHER	link
iMAGO	link
OPTOMICS	link
3* star reference site in EIPonAHA	link
European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) - RAISE HE project	link
EMMA Master	link

Other initiatives considered for networking and clustering:

- The European Partnership for Personalised Medicine;
- International Consortium for Personalised Medicine, ICPeMed;
- European Research Area Network on Personalised Medicine;
- PROPHET.

Key expected outcomes through the project implementation period:

- Not less than **4 networking/joint initiatives**.

Towards the end of the project, a large clustering workshop will be organised for the demonstration of the final and validated version of the digital health ecosystem to representatives of the aforementioned groups of stakeholders (**Paragraph 2.5.1.**).

2.4.4 Media

The Media means are key tools to transmit information about the project to other stakeholders and the general public. They have a lot of influence and may have a positive impact to increase results, raise awareness and offer information to the rest of the society about the iPROLEPSIS project.

The media-based communication aims to increase results, raise awareness and offer information to stakeholders (i.e., patients, hospitals, clinicians, associations, municipalities, etc.) and will be based on four different communication activities:

- Newsletters;
- Website/blog posts;
- Social media posts;
- Major media (TV/radio).

Communication on project website and social media accounts have started from the beginning of the project. It is expected every month to populate 2 posts on project's social media accounts and website.

In addition, a quarterly newsletter will be shared to inform about the achievements/news of the iPROLEPSIS project. It is planned to prepare and distribute 16 newsletters in total. Newsletters will be uploaded on the website and social media accounts.

To distribute newsletters, the European platform of news CORDIS WIRE might be considered as well to win audiences and optimize project's news and information.

Major media will be involved from M36, when tangible results of the project are available. It is expected 5 press releases in national and 2 press releases in EU-level media to be distributed.

2.4.5 PsA educational content development

Educational content aiming to enhance the health literacy and awareness of patients diagnosed with PsA and people at increased risk will be created in close collaboration with project's clinical partners. The content will be targeted to specialist and non-specialist audiences and language adapted accordingly.

Key information on disease characteristics as well as on actionable factors and treatments that can reduce inflammation and positively impact quality of life will be communicated through printed material, dedicated newsletters, disease/treatment-specific webinars, and the personalised interfaces of the digital health ecosystem's mobile apps.

Dissemination tools for educational content promotion:

- **Videos** (interviews with patients / healthcare professionals / iPROLEPSIS researchers);
- **Written content** answering the defined questions via the project's website and social media;
- **Participation in patient events.**

Educational material will be uploaded on project website, social media accounts and project applications.

2.5 Communication activities

2.5.1 Analysis of stakeholders

The target audiences for iPROLEPSIS communication, dissemination and outreach include society at large, including citizens, patients, HCPs, relevant R&I projects and policy makers, at EU and national level. The dissemination and communication actions target all involved, interested, and potential audiences to increase the impact of the different dimensions of the project.

Based on the iPROLEPSIS project goals and identified target groups (**Table 5**), the list of stakeholders has been identified and will be reached via different dissemination and communication tools and channels.

The main target groups of iPROLEPSIS are:

- the relevant scientists and engineers;
- the relevant industries;
- the policy makers;
- the patients, their families and carers and their associations;
- citizens at large.

Table 5 Target groups

Main target groups	Target audience	Objectives	Dissemination & Communication channels
Academia and relevant scientists and engineers	This group targets all research communities interested in the project's developments, results and innovation which can be beneficiary for their own research activities: (research scientists, biologists, biochemists, pharmacists clinicians and AI engineers)	Communicate scientific findings and take feedback; Transfer of knowledge; Raise awareness; Building a community/forum; Get support from the scientific community; Boost the project sustainability through the development of new related research projects; Extend network	Scientific conferences; Events; Workshops; Mailing list; Special sessions; Seminars; Publications in peer-reviewed journals

Industry	Biomedical technology and pharmaceutical	Inform industry about the project's vision and exchange ideas; Extend network; Demonstrate the business potential; push towards adoption of iPROLEPSIS products and services; Collect feedback on expectations and requirement to adjust commercial exploitation plans; Convince about the technical feasibility and competitiveness of concept and tools developed;	Business/Industry events, and EXPOs stands/booths; mailing list; Publication in business magazines
Individuals and associations of people with/at risk of PsA, families and carers	The patients, their families and carers and their associations	Project involvement; General awareness; Increase engagement of the participants of the studies;	Clinical focus groups; Newsletters; Social media; Website; Major media presence
Policy makers	This is a wide group encompassing innovation driven local, regional, national authorities, representatives & associations, Ministries, parliaments and national & international Public Administrations.	Project involvement; Attract the interest of relevant stakeholders	Website; Social media; Newsletters; Major media presence
General public	The general public consists of a general audience and other actors not identified as direct targeted groups by the project, though this group can have strong interest in the project: citizen Interest Groups, NGOs, Community Action Groups.	General awareness Project progress	Website; Social media; Newsletters; Major media presence

To reach out to the largest possible audience, iPROLEPSIS partners will also use their own network of contacts at the local, national, European and international level (Table 6). This list will be constantly updated during the whole duration of the project.

Table 6 List of research and business networks

Category	Relevant Network/Association
Health	Industry: Biopharma SRL, ATTUROS Limited, Novartis, Oxford Biodynamics Limited, Pfizer Limited, Bristol-Myers Squibb Company Corp

	<p>Associations: Group for Research and Assessment of Psoriasis and Psoriatic Arthritis (GRAPPA), European Alliance of Associations for Rheumatology (EULAR), OMERACT, Dutch Arthritis Foundation, Greek Arthritis Foundation, Portuguese Arthritis Foundation, Health Cluster Portugal, European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), European Hospital and Healthcare Federation (HOPE), The EuroSPA Collaboration Network (EuroSpa), Metadata registry for the ERN-RITA (MeRITA), European Health Data & Evidence Network (EHDEN), International, observational database METEOR, Health Cluster Portugal, European Network of Living Labs, Bayerische Landesärztekammer, Medical Association from Thessaloniki, TUM Graduate School, Deutschen Zentrum für Herz-Kreislauf-Forschung (PI, DZHK), Deutsche Gesellschaft für Gefäßchirurgie und Gefäßmedizin (DGG), Munich Heart Alliance (MHA), European Society of Molecular Imaging (ESMI)</p>
Computer science/engineering	<p>Industry: Philips Medical Systems, VIMAR SPA, F6S Network Ireland Ltd, ECLEXYS SAGL, Green Communications SAS, Mubadala, Dell, IBM, Microsoft, Cosmote, DT.</p> <p>Associations: The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data, European Alliance for Medical and Biological Engineering & Science (EAMBES), International Federation for Medical and Biological Engineering (IFMBE), EIT Health, European Federation for Medical Informatics (EFMI)</p>

2.5.2 Language

Structuring audiences has real impacts on what communication the project produce and how it is written, designed and distributed. For example:

- **Language style:** The language style used in the different communication context will vary, generally becoming more specialized at deeper levels. Technical communication, therefore, has its place, but not in dissemination and communication context written for public community (unless it is requested);
- **Design style:** This is equally true for design issues. In essence, it may be counter-productive, as well as a waste of resources, to design a report aimed at highly specialized audiences as a glossy product, covered with a multitude of images and illustrations. In this case, the product type is inappropriate for both the audience and the message.

For each audience the following questions will tried to be answered and the language of message will be adapted:

- Why do they need to know?
- What makes the issue urgent?
- What are the consequences if no action is taken?
- What solutions are we offering?
- How does our work relate to everyday life?
- Does it link to any broader societal issue?

Rather than focusing only on the provision of factual information, we will try as much as possible to position research topics within a broader socio-economic and policy context, so that it will be easier to explain the results and their relevance to both policymakers and citizens.

2.5.3 iPROLEPSIS brand identity

The project branding aims at helping all partners to communicate about the project in a uniform, consistent, and professional manner. The first communication action developed after the start of the project was to create a recognisable brand of iPROLEPSIS reflecting the main

goals of the initiative and offering to the audience/stakeholders a clear identification of the values and messages.

The iPROLEPSIS logo (**Figure 3**), an easily recognisable (visual) identity of the project which depicts the title of the project combined with an attention-grabbing first letter that merges different colours, was created. The overall image is forming a solid logo with imagery representative of healthcare theme, Arthritis' purple ribbon, and smart innovations. These images are combining the content of the iPROLEPSIS project.

Figure 3 iPROLEPSIS logo

The project's colour palette corresponding with the project's logo colours will be used throughout the iPROLEPSIS' templates and dissemination material (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4 iPROLEPSIS colour palette

2.5.4 Communication channels

With the main aim of attracting and establishing a iPROLEPSIS community of interest, main communication channels were established:

- **iPROLEPSIS website** that will serve as the main communication tool;
- **Social media accounts** (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook) that will serve as main channels to populate project news and achievements.

2.5.4.1 Website

The project website (<https://www.iprolepsis.eu>) is the main communication tool for the wide dissemination of the project activities, deliverables, and outcomes.

The project's website aims to meet the following objectives throughout the lifetime of the iPROLEPSIS project and after it:

- **Present** the iPROLESIS towards external stakeholders, sharing the main objectives of the project, describing the information related to the development and also the results and the barriers to overcome;
- **Connect** with additional interested stakeholders which might lead to potential synergies and initiatives;
- **Share information** about the project's progress, the news from different dissemination activities, and public documents/deliverables;
- **Provide access** to the dissemination and communication material ("press kit") for consortium partners and interested stakeholders, allowing the download of project material and documents.

The website is setup within a flowing process, i.e., Home, About, Partners, News, Press Kit, and Contact Us sub-pages. It will be frequently updated with new input, e.g., news of the project, meetings, participation in events, developments, etc. The website is also used to provide downloads of the dissemination material.

The website provides an easy and visually attractive outlet for communicating the project's objectives and results to the wide audiences. Furthermore, social media to be used by the consortium (Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter) and newsletters as means of communication of the project is also presented on the website. The information provided at the web portal is an outcome of all iPROLEPSIS project partners' contributions.

The healthcare theme and the image of personal care are also highlighted by the background video of the website, which is displayed on the 'Home' page (**Figure 5**) and disappears by scrolling the website.

Figure 5 iPROLEPSIS website's Home page

Together with social media, the website is a key tool for reaching out to a wide audience, communicate about the project and its results.

2.5.4.2 Social media accounts

Social media channels will be used to inform and connect with professionals, policymakers and the scientific community as well as to reach out to the general public.

Three social media account on **LinkedIn, Facebook and Twitter** are already created and updated:

Table 7 Social media channels

Social media channel	iPROLEPSIS link in the channel
LinkedIn	@iProlepsis
Twitter	@iprolepsis
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/iPROLEPSIS

The iPROLEPSIS project's social media accounts (**Figure 6**) are linked with the iPROLEPSIS website and accessible by clicking the Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter icons on the project's website. Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter accounts can be accessed using the 'handle' @iprolepsis.

Figure 6 iPROLEPSIS website's Home page

It is expected that these different social media accounts will contribute to developing a community of people interested in how the project aims to improve care for people with psoriatic arthritis (PsA). These platforms will help raise awareness about the project's objectives, showcase its progress, and foster interaction with related initiatives.

2.5.5 iPROLEPSIS communication kit

The following communication materials were prepared and distributed to all project partners in order to ensure effective communication and increase public awareness of the project:

- Flyer;
- Poster;
- Roll-up banner.

A project flyer (**Figure 8**) with general information on the project was created at month 3. This will be used at future events the consortium is organizing or participating in.

Figure 7 iPROLEPSIS flyer

A project poster and roll-up banner (Figure 7 and Figure 9) will be used during external conferences and events attended by the consortium to promote and present the results arising from the project.

Figure 8 iPROLEPSIS poster

Figure 9 iPROLEPSIS roll-up

It should be noted that the material presented in **Figure 7 - Figure 9** is an updated version of the communication kit included in the deliverable D6.1 “Project branding and communication channel”.

2.6 Impact assessment

Monitoring the impact of the different dissemination and communication activities implies a systematic collection of data and reporting of information from all partners. This information is needed to assess the success of the dissemination and communication strategy.

The communication and dissemination objectives will be reached through the activities of all partners: individually, through each partner’s entity activities; and collectively, through the partner’s contribution to the global strategy with the goal to reach the stakeholders of the project and build the iPROLEPSIS community.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have also been defined to measure the impact of each dissemination and communication activity. KPIs are measuring factors for the performance and progress of an activity, message, task, etc. towards its expected impact. KPIs will be used to assess the performance of the dissemination and communication activities all along the project duration and re-orientate the dissemination and communication plan, if necessary, when KPIs are not met and the expected impact is not reached.

Table 8 KPIs table

Dissemination and communication actions	What	KPIs
Publications	Peer-reviewed journals	20 publications
	Business Magazines	4 publications
Event participation	Scientific conference presentations/ posters	20 presentations/posters
	Business/Industry events, and EXPOs stands/booths	3 events
	Workshops/ Special sessions/ Seminars	8 events 50 expected attendees
	Clinical focus groups with patients	6 focus groups
Media presence	Newsletters	1000 subscribers
	Website/blog posts	2 posts/month 1000 visitors/month
	Social media posts	2 posts/month 2000 followers
	Major media (TV/radio) presence	5 presences in national media 2 presences in EU-level media
Networking and clustering events		≥4 networking/joint initiatives

All the impacts will be compiled in three deliverables D6.3 “First report on project visibility and educational material” (M18), D6.5 “Midterm report on project visibility and education material” (M32) and D6.6 “Final report on project visibility and education material” at the end of the project (M48).

2.6.1 Tracking and monitoring of the actions

SMARTSOL SIA will oversee the task of tracking all the dissemination and communication activities of the partners. At this scope, a tracking form (**Figure 10**) was created to gather information related to the dissemination and communication activities implemented by each partner, namely:

- Publications;
- Event participation;
- Media presence;
- Networking and clustering events;
- Education content development.

All partners will be reminded to update it as soon as they are involved in a communication or dissemination action to keep track of all the activities implemented within iPROLEPSIS.

At the end of each reporting period, this document will allow to elaborate a dissemination impact analysis to evaluate the impact of the actions, the type and number of people reached and to check if KPIs planned have been met. If not, corrective measures will be undertaken.

Dissemination pillar	Communication channel	Name/description of activity	Planned KPIs	Planned outreach level (attendees/visitors/subscribers)	Who (partner's name)	Date	Place	Number of people reached	Outreach level (International / European / Regional)
Publications	Peer-reviewed journals		20						
	Business Magazines		4						
Event participation	Scientific conference presentations/ poster		20						
	Business/Industry events, and EXPOs stands/booths		3						
	Workshops/ Special sessions/ Seminar		8	50					
	Clinical focus groups with patients		6						
	Networking/clustering initiatives		4						
Media presence	Newsletters		16	1000 subscribers					
	Website/blog posts		96	1000/month					
	Social media posts		96	2000 followers					
	Major media (TV/radio) presence		7						
Educational content development	Videos/printed material/other								

Figure 10 KPIs tracking form.

2.7 Dissemination and communication rules

2.7.1 Acknowledgment of funding and disclaimer

Communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and or major result must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (Figure 11) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Figure 11 EU logo

The European Commission's support of the iPROLEPSIS project must be acknowledged in all the dissemination and communication tools and materials including the following disclaimer:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

2.7.2 Prior notice Protocol

iPROLEPSIS project partners must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

2.7.3 Open access to scientific publications and scientific data

iPROLEPSIS supports the Open Science approach and understands the need to make scientific research and its dissemination accessible to all levels of an inquiring society,

amateur or professional. To deliver trustworthy, transparent AI tools, the project will adopt a series of practices to ensure rapid, wide access to its research methods, data, and outcomes.

The project will ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. Furthermore, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) will specifically refer to the support of the EC.

Regarding the scientific publications, the Open Research Europe² platform will be used, supporting openness in all stages of a publications' life cycle. To maximise visibility, research teams will also target scientific journals with high impact factor and Green or Gold open access.

Through FAIR³ management and sharing, the project will further provide access at least to the research datasets it generated for developing/validating its AI models and digital biomarkers (dBMs). Other heterogenous research assets, i.e., clinical study protocols, design reports, and algorithms, are also considered paramount in ensuring reliability/reproducibility and therefore actions will be taken to provide timely access to them.

Study protocols will be registered early in ClinicalTrials.gov or the ISRCTN registry, data analysis algorithms and ML workflows will be uploaded with appropriate licences (subject to IP rights) to open repositories (e.g., GitHub), while co-creation and design sprint reports will be accessible via research portals (e.g., Zenodo). To translate the needs of relevant end-users into its products and foster uptake, the project will also adopt citizen science concepts, by enabling end-users to shape research questions underlying the development of the AI models, through its co-creation process.

2.8 Exploitation strategy

In accordance with the Grant Agreement, each beneficiary must – up to four years after the period end of the project – take measures aiming to ensure exploitation of its results (either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing).

In the present deliverable the initial exploitation strategy and activities envisaged to assess the commercialization and applicability of the concepts and ideas central to the evolution of the project results are presented.

Several individual key exploitable results (KERs) are expected to be generated in the project, directly and indirectly. The iPROLEPSIS direct KERs consist of:

- Datasets;
- AI models and (digital) biomarkers;
- Software (SW) applications;
- Hardware (HW) components;
- an integrated healthcare platform (ecosystem).

Moreover, the project execution might produce a set of **indirect KERs** such as results of clinical trials, the infrastructure that supports the development (i.e., data management and Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery – CI/CD), and the methodology framework (i.e., expertise for co-creation process, interdisciplinary research, agile management, data management plan – DMP).

² Open Research Europe - Open Access Publishing Platform <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

³ FAIR stands for: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability

All KERs constitute the project's value proposition and form a value chain. The KERs are interrelated and can be exploited as one business unit and/or separately. The individual exploitation does not only regard financing and sales but also means investing in research, i.e., increasing scientific impact, extending network and future research funding pursuit. The pathway followed will be analysed during the project in the exploitation planning activities.

Figure 12 iPROLEPSIS value proposition, KERs and value chain

Exploitation, business planning and IPR management activities will leverage consortium technological leadership and business networks in the AI and technology sector, as well as technology transfer offices of technical academic partners.

The exploitation strategy over the course of the project will be based on four main steps:

- specify KERs and evaluate the exploitation potential of these outcomes;
- define target stakeholders, market, clients and users;
- identify most appropriate IPR strategies;
- where relevant, prepare business plans for the implemented innovations.

Exploitation and IPR management activities have already started but they will be intensified the second half of the project. To facilitate the identification and assessment of the first exploitable results, a preliminary internal survey based on the EC Innovation Radar methodology will be employed.

Based on consultation activities between involved partners, the IPR Manager and key external stakeholders, the resulting exploitation plan will be elaborated in close cooperation with all partners and incorporating strategic feedback from external experts from industry, healthcare and academia.

Throughout the project implementation, all partners will contribute to the identification of results that may qualify for IPR protection by continuous analysis of output progress within WPs, allowing rapid application to the European Patent Office (EPO) where relevant. Patenting and other protective procedures will proceed along the regulations set forth in the Consortium Agreement on a royalty-free basis.

Table 9 Key exploitable results and exploitation goals

KER	Ownership (Individual/Joint)	Type	Exploitation goal	Time to market/ Maturity time
Datasets	Joint	Open access, Usage rights	New projects, Publications	1-2 years
AI models/ biomarkers	Individual/Joint	Commercial, Usage rights	Spin-off, New projects, Publications	3-5 years
SW apps/ HW components	Individual	Commercial	Spin-off, Revenue	3-5 years
Integrated platform (ecosystem)	Individual/Joint	Commercial	Spin-off, Revenue	3-5 years
Clinical validation results	Individual/Joint	Non-commercial	Patents, Publications, New projects	1-3 years
Infrastructure	Individual	Commercial	Spin-off; Revenue	1-5 years
Methodology framework	Joint	Open access, Usage rights	New projects, Publications	1-3 years

The exploitation methodology will be implemented during the 4 years of the iPROLEPSIS project, intensifying the efforts dedicated as soon as the results are more consistent and technologically mature.

Led by industry and SME partners, the consortium will **specify the exploitable assets and develop joint and individual exploitation plans**, based on thorough socio-economic/market analysis and agreed IPRs. Partners with knowledge of the regulatory framework, through timely liaison with concerned bodies and in close collaboration with clinical and technical partners, will **develop the roadmap for regulatory approval** of the minimum viable products (MVPs).

With respect to **regulatory approval (T6.4)**, the requirements and the roadmap will be **defined**, after liaison with concerned regulatory bodies, for the iPROLEPSIS digital care tools to receive Medical Device (Class I, II) CE certification within five years after the end of the project. Regulatory requirements for other countries (e.g., FDA clearance) will also be outlined.

Regarding exploitation, an **in-depth socioeconomic and market analysis** will be performed, focusing on the landscape of available technology-based solutions for PsA management. Further, in collaboration with T1.5 “Innovation and intellectual property management”, **exploitable outcomes of the project will be identified** and the **means for their concrete use and delivery to the market will be explored**, through definition of individual exploitation plans and development of joint exploitation schemes, including detailed business plans.

Finally, the **cost effectiveness of the iPROLEPSIS digital care tools will be evaluated** using the MAFEIP tool.

Expected exploitation KPIs to be reached over the course of the project:

- **≥2 joint exploitation plans;**
- **≥10 individual exploitation plans;**

- **1 regulatory approval plan.**

Reports, focusing on results and activities implemented will be provided as deliverables D6.4 “Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (initial version)” (M 27) and D6.7 “Exploitation and regulatory approval plan (final version)” (M 48).

In a next step, however, we must deliberate about how to create impact from exploitation. Regarding exploitation as a proxy for impact is not correct, since exploitation is a short-term effect, whereas impact is characterised as a long-lasting and observable change in/at/onto the desired object. Impact is often not predictable, as it depends on multiple variables that influence its likelihood to occur. With a view on this deliverable and the rather early phase of the project’s implementation, we provide a list of EC services to support exploitation in Horizon Europe (HORIZON) projects.

Usually, these services are free of charge for beneficiaries and are on offer both for individual projects and project groups, in case several projects can be accommodated under a joint topic. Depending on the type of service, these are the most common ways of support offered:

- Providing support in effective dissemination and raising the exploitation potential of research results generated, in particular what concerns project strategies on dissemination, business plan development or going-to-the-market;
- Providing a platform to publish and promote research results targeting a broad range of stakeholders (from business to academia);
- Providing advice on how to spark thinking in an “innovation mindset” within a project context and support in identification of innovation actors relevant to the project.

With a view on our specific needs (some of which might only arise at a later stage of the project), it is important to be aware of them first. Whether the project will in fact request support from any or more of these services, remains to be seen. We consider it more useful to access these services just in case a real need emerges from our dissemination and exploitation actions, so to allow us receiving tailored support, rather than to send very general requests without any further context.

1. Horizon Results Booster

Mission statement: “Horizon Results Booster – Steering research towards strong societal impact, concretising the value of R&I activity for societal challenges”.

Type: Support to strategy development in dissemination and exploitation, business development and go-to-market Management: META Group with further partners.

Website: <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

For iPROLEPSIS, the following services are on offer:

- For single projects support in exploitation of research results;
- For project groups support in disseminating research results;
- Support in the development of a business plan and to attract additional funding for implementing project results after the project’s end;
- Support in preparing project results for commercialization.

2. Innovation Radar

Mission statement: “Our goal is to allow every citizen, public official, professional and business person to discover the outputs of EU innovation funding and give them a chance to seek out innovators who could follow in the footsteps of companies such as Skype, TomTom, ARM Holdings, all of whom received EU funding in their early days”.

Type: Providing advice on how to spark thinking in an “innovation mindset” within a project context and support in identification of innovation actors relevant to the project; Identification of high-potential innovations and innovators in EU-funded R&I projects.

Website: <https://www.innoradar.eu/>

For IPROLEPSIS, the Innovation Radar might be interesting because of three main reasons:

- To understand how real innovations emerge from EU funded projects: what are typical patterns leading to innovations in EU-funded projects? What are drivers, enablers, obstacles?
- To get an idea where the innovators are located, and about their features on the market → get-in-touch for creation of synergies, knowledge transfer, fostering European networks;
- To search for innovations and partners related to it in the field of PsA → get-in-touch for creation of synergies, knowledge transfer, fostering European networks.

3. Open Research Europe platform

Type: An open access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon Europe (HORIZON) projects and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including an open peer review and article.

Website: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/publish-your-research>

4. Horizon Results platform

Mission: “Turning Europe's research results into innovations which generate value for economy, society and contribute to a sustainable future”.

Type: A platform for showcasing research results, finding collaboration opportunities and getting inspired by the results of others. Publishing results is part of the project execution for which all partners are responsible.

Website: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

5. European Standardisation Booster Service for EU Projects

Mission: To support EU Research and Innovation projects to valorise results through standardisation and address urgencies identified in the EU Strategy on Standardisation.

Type: Provides consultancy services to guide and support beneficiaries and consortia of R&I projects to make sure they take the right strategic approach and contribute efficiently to the Standardisation process and to make them active players in the development of Standards in the corresponding area or domain.

Website: <http://hsbooster.eu/>

6. Horizon IP Scan

Horizon IP Scan is a tailored, free-of-charge, first-line IP support service provided by the European Commission specifically designed to help European start-ups and other SMEs involved in EU-funded collaborative research projects to efficiently manage and valorise IP in collaborative R&I efforts.

The overall objective is to help SMEs address central IP issues that may arise at different stages of a collaborative research project.

Horizon IP Scan entails three major steps:

1. a preparation phase including a pre-interview;
2. the main interview, which is done in an in-person or online meeting;
3. and the provision of a report and recommendations.

Website: https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/services/horizon-ip-scan_en

3 Conclusions

This document establishes the guidelines for the common dissemination, exploitation and communication strategies in the project. It is intended to give an overview of the types of dissemination, exploitation and communication actions planned during the project, valorise the results of the project, and bring it to the public and to the market.

This is a document for the use of all the partners involved in iPROLEPSIS project, designated as “public” regarding the dissemination level. Among others, it describes in detail the stakeholders, actions, tools, materials, KPIs and procedures agreed and being a live document, it will be modified according to the project needs, keeping updated the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies of the project.